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An immune receptor activated in metastasis to the CNS in humans, VSTM2L.

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Vstm2l operated in a cellular context governed by neuronal gene expression (the pre- and post-synaptic vesicle protein SNAP91, GFRA2, and Neurod6), specific co-receptor expression including LRRTM4, IGSF21, LINGO1, and the HMP19 molecule.